

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Influence of habitat quality and resource density on breeding-season female monarch butterfly (*Danaus plexippus*) movement and space use in north-central USA agroecosystem landscapes

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S1. Field Site Characteristics

Vegetation surveys were conducted along 100 m transects (S2) in mid-July 2019 at the mosaic site and mid-July 2020 at the roadside sites. Surveys included estimates of vegetation diversity with 0.5 m² Daubenmire frames (S3), vegetation height with Robel poles (S3), and abundance of milkweed ramets and blooming inflorescences (S4). Based on orthophoto images and results from these surveys, areas within our three sites with > 5 resources/m², < 3 resources/m², and 0 resources/m² were classified as “high-density habitat”, “low-density habitat”, and zero-density habitat”, respectively (Table 1; see Fig 1); the 5 m buffer of the linear edge of each habitat class was classified as “habitat edge”. The mosaic site consisted of 37.9% zero-density habitat (ZD), 23.6% high-density habitat (HD), 32.6% low-density habitat (LD), and 5.6% habitat edges (HE). Together the roadside sites consisted of 94.0% ZD, 2.0% HD, 2.1% LD, and 1.9% HE.

S2. Locations of 100 m transects to estimate milkweed and blooming plant abundances at the mosaic site (A) and the prairie habitat near the roadside (B). Transects are labeled to correspond with S3-S4. Note there is no transect 10.

S3. Daubenmire and Robel surveys were conducted every 10 m along the 100 m transect laid at the 14 locations (note no location 10) at the mosaic field site (see S2) and the one location at the Anderson-Dyas remnant prairie at the roadside with high-density habitat site (see S2). Table includes the average percent of cover of the 10 Daubenmire frame (0.5 m²) estimates of grasses, forbs, bare ground, and litter. At the same locations along the transect, estimates of vegetation height to the nearest 10 cm were made with a Robel pole from 4 m directly north, east, south, and west of the pole. Table includes the average of all Robel estimates for each transect.

Transect	% Grass	% Forb	% Bare Ground	% Litter	Litter Depth	Robel
1	76.6	1.7	10.0	98.0	2.6	2.9
2	59.0	3.2	16.7	94.5	3.1	3.7
3	62.4	1.6	16.0	98.0	9.1	3.5
4	62.8	1.7	16.7	96.8	8.3	3.6
5	38.6	42.4	5.0	93.2	6.6	7.2
6	40.8	38.3	41.7	62.2	1.0	3.5
7	81.3	0.4	33.5	55.6	4.7	5.1
8	64.9	9.4	25.1	62.5	1.8	4.8
9	39.2	35.5	41.5	50.7	0.7	6.2
11	76.9	1.9	63.0	16.0	0.1	6.7
12	57.7	28.3	63.0	19.4	0.2	4.9
13	75.7	15.1	13.4	98.0	7.9	3.5
14	73.2	5.4	63.3	30.9	3.2	4.8
15	62.8	16.5	4.7	90.8	3.5	4.9
16	26.2	70.6	16.0	86.0	2.8	9.5

S4. The number of milkweed ramets and blooming inflorescences within a 1 m band along the 14 transects at the mosaic field site and the one transect in the Anderson-Dyas remnant prairie at the roadside with high-density habitat site (see S2). Table also provides density classifications including the density of resources in the area and the corresponding habitat class category (HD or LD).

Plant Species	Plant Common Name	Transect Identification															
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	11	12	13	14	15	16	
<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	Common Milkweed (ramets)	2	2	3	10	231	41	6	8	6	0	4	59	0	64	5	
<i>Asclepias incarnata</i>	Swamp Milkweed (ramets)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Asclepias verticillata</i>	Butterfly Milkweed (ramets)	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	Eastern Daisy Fleabane	5	0	0	0	220	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	
<i>Daucus carota</i>	Queen Ann's Lace	0	2	0	0	0	96	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Lactuca canadensis</i>	Canada Lettuce	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Monarda fistulosa</i>	Wild Bergamot	0	0	0	0	539	0	0	0	1134	0	937	92	0	1316	288	
<i>Rudbeckia triloba</i>	Brown Eyed Susan	0	0	0	0	1141	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	240	0	
<i>Ratibida pinnata</i>	Greyheaded Coneflower	0	0	0	0	362	0	0	0	113	0	226	165	0	345	66	
<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i>	Black Eyed Susan	0	0	0	0	135	0	0	0	63	0	6	0	0	0	0	
<i>Heliopsis helianthoides</i>	Oxeye Sunflower	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	111	0	0	9	83	
<i>Echinacea pallida</i>	Pale Purple Coneflower	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Oenothera biennis</i>	Common Evening Primrose	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Melilotus albus</i>	White Sweet Clover	0	0	0	0	0	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	
<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Canada Thistle	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	115	0	24	2	0	24	0	0	
<i>Polygonum sp.</i>	Smartweed	0	0	0	0	0	124	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Pastinaca sativa</i>	Wild Parsnip	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	212	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	
<i>Pycnanthemum virginianum</i>	Virginia Mountain Mint	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	0	0	0	0	0	57	
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Verbena stricta</i>	Hoary Vervain	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Melilotus officinalis</i>	Yellow Sweet Clover	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	Common St. Johnswort	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	
Density Classification	resources/m ²	0.07	0.05	0.03	0.10	26.37	3.30	0.07	3.45	13.45	0.24	12.86	3.32	0	19.74	5.47	
	Habitat Class	LD	LD	LD	LD	HD	HD	LD	LD	HD	LD	HD	HD	LD	HD	HD	

S5. Release locations at the mosaic site (A), RHD (B), and RLD (C) represented by stars. Red stars are release locations with less than four responsive monarchs. Green stars are locations with four or more responsive monarchs. Location 1, 5, and 11 were within MLD; location 2, 6, and 10 were within MHD; locations 3 and 8 were in MHE; locations 4, 7 and 9 were within MZD; locations 12 and 13 were within the grassy vegetation along secondary gravel rights of way. Monarchs released in MHD south of the crop field (location 6) had a directional pattern north-north-east toward HD (Rayleigh test of uniformity: test statistic = 0.4699, $P = 0.0537$; mean direction of movement = 7.4°). Monarchs released in MHE between the east side of the ZD and the west side of HD (location 8) had a directional pattern southeast toward HD (Rayleigh test of uniformity: test statistic = 0.5512, $P = 0.0031$; mean direction of movement = 137.0°).

S6. The combined number of radio-tagged and untagged female monarchs released in the mosaic and roadside sites that flew or were unresponsive (UNR; no movement within 15 minutes of release).

Treatment	Flew	UNR	Total	% UNR
Radio-tagged	105	33	138	23.9
Untagged	44	13	57	22.8
Overall	149	46	195	23.6

S7. The number of female monarchs released in each of the release habitat classes that flew or were unresponsive (UNR; no movement within 15 minutes of release).

Release Habitat Class	Flew	UNR	Total	% UNR
MLD	20	2	22	9.1
MHD	18	7	25	28.0
MZD	18	4	22	18.2
MHE	19	14	33	42.4
RZD	30	8	38	21.1
RHD	44	11	55	20.0
Mosaic Total	75	27	102	26.5
Roadside Total	74	19	93	20.4
Total	149	46	195	23.6

S8. Two-dimensional ordination of the first two principle components (PCs) from a principle components analysis of temperature, wind speed, and days held in captivity for radio-tagged female monarchs that flew (responsive; red) or remained stationary (unresponsive; blue) within 15 minutes of release at the mosaic site and within 30 minutes of the first step at the roadside sites. Only variables with a correlation greater than ± 0.852 are included in the interpretation of the axes.

Although trials were conducted within environmental thresholds (e.g. temperature between 18.6 and 35.4°C; wind speed below 15.0 kph), factors reported as measurement variables could influence monarch responsiveness. A principle components analysis (PCA) was used as an exploratory, graphical tool to discern if differences in monarch responsiveness were related to temperature and wind speed at trial initiation, days held in captivity prior to trial initiation, and monarch mass. Because 52 of 195 monarchs were not recovered after their trial, their mass is unknown. Consequently, these individuals were removed from the initial PCA. Variables with a correlation greater than ± 0.852 for PC1, PC2, PC3, and PC4 were temperature (-0.887), wind speed (-0.852), days captive (0.975), and monarch mass (0.989), respectively. PC1, PC2, PC3, and PC4 accounted for 52.65, 44.72, 2.575 and 0.045% of the variation. Because the principle component most closely related to monarch mass (PC4) accounted for 0.045% of the variance, a second PCA was done with all 195 individuals excluding mass as a variable. In this analysis, PC1 accounted for 49.68% of the variance and displayed a positive relationship with wind speed (0.961). PC2 accounted for 47.71% of the variance and displayed a negative correlation with temperature (-0.958). Days held in captivity was the variable most correlated to PC3 (-0.981), which accounted for 2.6% of the total variance. A plot of PC1 and PC2 does not suggest distinctive clustering of responsive and unresponsive individuals (S10).

S9. Automated Radio Telemetry System (ARTS) at the mosaic field site

Visual observation and handheld radio telemetry were augmented with an automated radio telemetry system (Fisher et al. 2021) at the mosaic site. A square grid of nine towers, each separated by approximately 250 m, was employed to create 500 m² detection area within the 800 m² focal research area (see Fig 1a). Power readings collected with this system were stored and analyzed post-hoc in the laboratory; however, because of vegetation interference and limited power emitted by our transmitters, no location estimates were possible. Because of concern for investigator safety, limited personnel support consistent with Iowa State University SARS-CoV-2 safety protocols, and potential signal interference from utility lines, the tower system was not employed at the roadside sites.

To calibrate the ARTS in this field setting, data was collected from July 6-8, 2019 to generate power-distance and power-angle relationships. With all towers' automated receivers functioning, technicians stood for one minute while wearing a transmitter attached to a baseball cap at locations every 25 m on the diagonals from tower 2 to 4, 4 to 8, 8 to 6, and 6 to 2 for a total of 50 locations. Additionally, power data was collected at an additional 11-16 locations per tower arranged in semi-circles with a 25 m radius from each tower. Data associated with these tests can be found in the digital repository for with this project (<https://github.com/kelseyfisher/monarchoccurrence>).

In 2019 there were 13 days that radio tagged monarchs were released and observed while the 9-tower ARTS was powered to collect data. Across these days, 42 radio-tagged monarchs were observed for 300 – 5,400 s (5 – 90 min). The beats per minute (bpm) window of the transmitters was 36.8, hence, a power detection could theoretically be detected by one antenna on each tower every two seconds; i.e., 150 – 2,700 power detections for each tower. Actual power detections were much lower than these theoretical maximum 'hits.' The largest percent of total successful power detections of the anticipated detections was 22%, followed by 12% and 7%. Power readings either came from two towers over a long period of time or scattered in time across up to 6 towers. Of the 42 butterflies, six (14.3%) had zero power detections from any of the towers. Two towers (1 and 4) never detected power during times when monarch butterfly trials were conducted. Because of the limited power readings that were detected were either from two or fewer towers or did not overlap in time in this field configuration, we were unable to estimate any locations with this system.

Similarly, few location estimates were possible when a transmitter was attached to a butterfly under ideal environmental conditions with limited surrounding vegetation. As reported in Fisher et al. (2021), power can be dampened by 22 RSSI when vegetation surrounded the transmitter. Our findings in the mosaic field conditions further demonstrate the power emitted by the 0.22 g transmitter is not sufficiently strong enough to overcome signal dampening due to vegetation and/or orientation of the transmitter antenna.

S10. Quantifying Habitat & Space Use

Continuous-time movement models (ctmm) incorporate multiple measures to understand space use, such as georeferenced locations, time, and error. Additionally, ctmm aids in estimating an animal's location between sampling location fixes (i.e., between georeferenced locations). Movement models for individual monarchs were created with the 'continuous-time movement model' package (Calabrese et al. 2016, Fleming et al. 2016, Fleming and Calabrese 2020) in R (R Core Team 2020), and selected based on semivariogram estimates with the smallest AIC value. Models were generated for 96 monarchs (15/18 MZD, 12/19 MHE, 18/20 MLD, 15/18 MHD, 18/19 RZD, and 18/20 RHD) because 18 monarchs did not provide enough data to estimate uncertainty (e.g., observation period too short, too few georeferenced locations, long periods of time between known georeferenced locations). Output from occurrence models were raster images scaled from 0-1 with the probability of occurrence in each 0.05 m² cell. Occurrence raster images were clipped to raster images containing 0.05 m² cells scaled by habitat class to identify raster cells with non-zero occurrence probability in each habitat class with ArcMap 10.7. The number of raster cells with a non-zero probability of occurrence in each habitat class at the mosaic site, roadside sites, and each release habitat were summed (pooled), and the percent of cells in each habitat class were calculated and analyzed with multiple chi-square tests and a Bonferroni correction. The logit transformed proportions (Warton and Hui 2011) of raster cells with non-zero occurrence probability, time spent, and number of georeferenced locations in each habitat class were analyzed by spatial configuration and release habitat class with generalized linear models.

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S11. Occurrence probabilities (shaded) and straight-line flight paths (black lines) for each monarch released in MHD; ctm were not calculated for ai, al, ap, and ay.

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S12. Occurrence probabilities (shaded) and straight-line flight paths (black lines) for each monarch released in MZD; ctmm were not calculated for bw, bz, ct, and dx.

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S13. Occurrence probabilities (shaded) and straight-line flight paths (black lines) for each monarch released in MHE; ctmm were not calculated for bb, bd, bg, bh, bj, bu, co, and da. Monarchs released in MHE were presented a choice to fly into high-density (HD) or zero-density (ZD) habitat. A significantly higher percentage of monarchs initially entered HD (12/19) versus ZD habitat (5/19) ($\chi^2 = 15.17$; $df = 1$; $P = 9.824e-05$); two immediately flew outside our research area.

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S14. Occurrence probabilities (shaded) and straight-line flight paths (black lines) for each monarch released in MLD; ctmm were not calculated for cw and do.

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S15. Occurrence probabilities (shaded) and straight-line flight paths (black lines) for each monarch released in RZD; ctm were not calculated for ew.

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S16. Occurrence probabilities (shaded) and straight-line flight paths (black lines) for each monarch released in RHD; ctm were not calculated for ec and fs.

S17. Percentages of non-zero occurrence probability of breeding-season female monarchs in each habitat class (colored bars; see Table 1 for abbreviations) estimated by the mean (\pm SD) of the individuals pooled (B) at the mosaic site, the roadside sites, and for each release habitat class. Significance at the 0.007 threshold to account for multiple comparisons is indicated within each release group by different letters above the bars in the same color (values in S18).

S18. The number of raster cells with a non-zero probability of occurrence in each habitat class at the mosaic site, roadside site, and each release habitat class were summed, and the percent of cells in each habitat class were calculated and analyzed with multiple chi-square tests. The logit transformed proportion of cells with non-zero occurrence probability in each habitat class at the mosaic site, roadside sites, and each release habitat were analyzed with generalized linear models.

Site	Release Habitat	Comparison	Percent of cells with non-zero occurrence probability in each habitat class <i>Sum of all monarchs</i>			Logit transformed proportion of cells with non-zero occurrence probability in each habitat class <i>Average of all monarchs</i>					
			χ^2	df	P	F ratio	Z ratio	df	P		
Mosaic	Pooled	ZD x LD x HD x HE	107.73	3	< 2.2e-16	13.691		3, 232	< 0.0001		
		ZD x HE	0.59811	1	0.43930		-1.554			1, 116	0.4049
		ZD x LD	2.5648	1	0.10930		-2.927			1, 116	0.0180
		ZD x HD	47.627	1	5.15E-12		-6.148			1, 116	< 0.0001
		HE x LD	5.387	1	0.02029		-1.373			1, 116	0.5166
		HE x HD	54.298	1	1.72E-13		-4.594			1, 116	< 0.0001
		LD x HD	32.58	1	1.14E-08		-3.221			1, 116	0.0070
Roadside	Pooled	ZD x LD x HD x HE	94.596	3	< 2.2e-16	2.477		3, 86	0.0594		
		ZD x HE	31.263	1	2.25E-08						
		ZD x LD	27.23	1	1.81E-07						
		ZD x HD	62.356	1	2.87E-15						
		HE x LD	0.20442	1	0.65120						
		HE x HD	12.277	1	0.00046						
		LD x HD	14.842	1	0.00012						
Mosaic	MZD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	111.97	3	< 2.2e-16	3.779		3, 56	0.0100		
		ZD x HE	0.34038	1	0.55960		2.468			1, 28	0.0651
		ZD x LD	0.58661	1	0.44370		2.969			1, 28	0.0158
		ZD x HD	46.977	1	7.18E-12		0.906			1, 28	0.8017
		HE x LD	1.7897	1	0.18100		0.501			1, 28	0.9588
		HE x HD	52.201	1	5.01E-13		-1.562			1, 28	0.4007
		LD x HD	39.795	1	2.82E-10		-2.063			1, 28	0.1653
Mosaic	MHE	ZD x LD x HD x HE	116.2	3	< 2.2e-16	20.045		3, 44	< 0.0001		
		ZD x HE	5.8285	1	0.01577		-4.704			1, 22	< 0.0001
		ZD x LD	3.7983	1	0.05131		-0.602			1, 22	0.9313
		ZD x HD	33.921	1	5.74E-09		-6.525			1, 22	< 0.0001
		HE x LD	0.2637	1	0.60760		4.101			1, 22	0.0002
		HE x HD	56.71	1	5.05E-14		-1.821			1, 22	0.2632
		LD x HD	52.402	1	4.52E-13		-5.922			1, 22	< 0.0001
Mosaic	MHD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	140.7	3	< 2.2e-16	54.661		3, 52	< 0.0001		
		ZD x HE	5.5613	1	0.01836		-2.606			1, 26	0.0452
		ZD x LD	18.852	1	1.41E-05		-1.358			1, 26	0.5258
		ZD x HD	74.676	1	< 2.2e-16		-11.558			1, 26	< 0.0001
		HE x LD	7.0819	1	0.00779		1.248			1, 26	0.5960
		HE x HD	59.141	1	1.47E-14		-8.952			1, 26	< 0.0001
		LD x HD	33.127	1	8.63E-09		-10.200			1, 26	< 0.0001
Mosaic	MLD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	188.66	3	< 2.2e-16	25.559		3, 68	< 0.0001		
		ZD x HE	5.3383	1	0.02086		-1.532			1, 34	0.4180
		ZD x LD	84.125	1	< 2.2e-16		-8.229			1, 34	< 0.0001
		ZD x HD	10.537	1	0.00117		-3.468			1, 34	0.0029
		HE x LD	69.384	1	< 2.2e-16		-6.697			1, 34	< 0.0001
		HE x HD	1.7022	1	0.19200		-1.935			1, 34	0.2132
		LD x HD	57.206	1	3.92E-14		4.761			1, 34	< 0.0001
Roadside	RHD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	24.521	3	1.95E-05	0.932		3, 45	0.4240		
		ZD x HE	2.0758	1	0.14970						
		ZD x LD	0.093712	1	0.75950						
		ZD x HD	20.956	1	4.70E-06						
		HE x LD	3.0356	1	0.08146						
		HE x HD	11.147	1	0.00084						
		LD x HD	23.357	1	1.35E-06						
Roadside	RZD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	119.02	3	< 2.2e-16	1.633		3, 37	0.1793		
		ZD x HE	38.604	1	5.19E-10						
		ZD x LD	37.423	1	9.51E-10						
		ZD x HD	70.176	1	< 2.2e-16						
		HE x LD	0.015484	1	0.90100						
		HE x HD	12.887	1	0.00033						
		LD x HD	13.549	1	0.00023						

S19. Percentages of mean time (\pm SD) in each habitat class (A) and mean number of georeferenced points in each habitat class (B) pooled at the mosaic site, pooled at the roadside sites, and for each release habitat class. Significance at the 0.007 threshold was used to account for multiple comparisons is indicated within each release group by different letters above the bars in the same color (values in S20).

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S20. The logit transformed proportion of time and georeferenced locations in each habitat class at the mosaic site, roadside site, and each release habitat were analyzed with generalized linear models.

Site	Release Habitat	Comparison	Logit transformed proportion of time in each habitat class <i>Average of all monarchs</i>				Logit transformed proportion of georeferenced locations in each habitat class <i>Average of all monarchs</i>			
			F ratio	Z ratio	df	P	F ratio	Z ratio	df	P
Mosaic	Pooled	ZD x LD x HD x HE	5.87		3, 296	0.0005	9.025		3, 296	< 0.0001
		ZD x HE		-1.169	1, 148	0.6462		-1.222	1, 148	0.6131
		ZD x LD		-0.910	1, 148	0.7997		-1.566	1, 148	0.3979
		ZD x HD		-3.969	1, 148	0.0004		-4.960	1, 148	< 0.0001
		HE x LD		0.260	1, 148	0.9939		-0.345	1, 148	0.9859
		HE x HD		-2.800	1, 148	0.0263		-3.738	1, 148	0.0011
		LD x HD		-3.060	1, 148	0.0119		-3.393	1, 148	0.0039
Roadside	Pooled	ZD x LD x HD x HE	5.87		3, 86	0.0005	17.918		3, 152	< 0.0001
		ZD x HE		-1.169	1, 45	0.6462		0.096	1, 76	0.9997
		ZD x LD		-0.910	1, 48	0.7997		-4.075	1, 76	0.0003
		ZD x HD		-3.969	1, 25	0.0004		3.226	1, 76	0.0069
		HE x LD		0.260	1, 61	0.9939		-4.171	1, 76	0.0002
		HE x HD		-2.800	1, 38	0.0263		3.129	1, 76	0.0095
		LD x HD		-3.060	1, 41	0.0119		7.300	1, 76	< 0.0001
Mosaic	MZD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	22.607		3, 68	< 0.0001	15.138		3, 68	< 0.0001
		ZD x HE		7.137	1, 34	< 0.0001		6.039	1, 34	< 0.0001
		ZD x LD		7.126	1, 34	< 0.0001		5.530	1, 34	< 0.0001
		ZD x HD		4.813	1, 34	< 0.0001		3.257	1, 34	0.0062
		HE x LD		-0.011	1, 34	1.0000		-0.509	1, 34	0.9570
		HE x HD		-2.324	1, 34	0.0926		-2.782	1, 34	0.0277
		LD x HD		-2.313	1, 34	0.0949		-2.273	1, 34	0.1044
Mosaic	MHE	ZD x LD x HD x HE	22.875		3, 72	< 0.0001	24.592		3, 72	< 0.0001
		ZD x HE		-7.046	1, 36	< 0.0001		-6.656	1, 36	< 0.0001
		ZD x LD		0.172	1, 36	0.9982		0.581	1, 36	0.9677
		ZD x HD		-3.009	1, 36	0.0140		-4.487	1, 36	< 0.0001
		HE x LD		7.218	1, 36	< 0.0001		7.237	1, 36	< 0.0001
		HE x HD		4.038	1, 36	0.0003		2.169	1, 36	0.1320
		LD x HD		-3.181	1, 36	0.0080		-5.069	1, 36	< 0.0001
Mosaic	MHD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	71.464		3, 68	< 0.0001	73.648		3, 68	< 0.0001
		ZD x HE		-1.550	1, 34	0.4074		-1.482	1, 34	0.4481
		ZD x LD		-0.434	1, 34	0.9726		-0.729	1, 34	0.8856
		ZD x HD		-12.545	1, 34	< 0.0001		-12.084	1, 34	< 0.0001
		HE x LD		1.116	1, 34	0.6794		0.754	1, 34	0.8751
		HE x HD		-10.995	1, 34	< 0.0001		-11.331	1, 34	< 0.0001
		LD x HD		-12.111	1, 34	< 0.0001		-12.084	1, 34	< 0.0001
Mosaic	MLD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	31.44		3, 76	< 0.0001	37.624		3, 76	< 0.0001
		ZD x HE		-0.886	1, 38	0.8123		-1.314	1, 38	0.5538
		ZD x LD		-8.799	1, 38	< 0.0001		-9.730	1, 38	< 0.0001
		ZD x HD		-2.688	1, 38	0.0362		-2.718	1, 38	0.0332
		HE x LD		-7.913	1, 38	< 0.0001		-8.416	1, 38	< 0.0001
		HE x HD		-1.802	1, 38	0.2723		-1.404	1, 38	0.4967
		LD x HD		6.111	1, 38	< 0.0001		7.012	1, 38	< 0.0001
Roadside	RHD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	20.746		3, 76	< 0.0001	8.641		3, 76	< 0.0001
		ZD x HE		-1.724	1, 38	0.3110		-2.283	1, 38	0.1021
		ZD x LD		-7.323	1, 38	< 0.0001		-4.704	1, 38	< 0.0001
		ZD x HD		-1.464	1, 38	0.4595		-0.740	1, 38	0.8809
		HE x LD		-5.599	1, 38	< 0.0001		-2.421	1, 38	0.0731
		HE x HD		0.260	1, 38	0.9938		1.543	1, 38	0.4119
		LD x HD		5.859	1, 38	< 0.0001		3.964	1, 38	0.0004
Roadside	RZD	ZD x LD x HD x HE	19.42		3, 72	< 0.0001	20.484		3, 72	< 0.0001
		ZD x HE		1.762	1, 36	0.2920		2.722	1, 36	0.0329
		ZD x LD		-3.401	1, 36	0.0037		-1.220	1, 36	0.6168
		ZD x HD		3.978	1, 36	0.0004		5.987	1, 36	< 0.0001
		HE x LD		-5.163	1, 36	< 0.0001		-3.942	1, 36	0.0005
		HE x HD		2.217	1, 36	0.1187		3.266	1, 36	0.0060
		LD x HD		7.379	1, 36	< 0.0001		7.208	1, 36	< 0.0001

S21. Histograms of step lengths for 114 breeding-season female monarchs released in all habitat classes; 0-50 m step lengths represented in 1 m bins (A) and 51-2,000 m step lengths represented in 25 m bins (B). Note the different y-axis scales for A and B.

S22. Distribution of Euclidian movement bearings relative to the wind direction for all monarchs (A) and bearing for steps ≥ 50 m relative to the wind direction (B). To make orientations comparable, the wind bearing was subtracted from the step's bearing: 360 was added to the bearings that were calculated to be < 0 ; 360 was subtracted from the bearings that were calculated to be > 360 . Therefore, the direction upwind is the wind bearing is consistently represented as 0° (dotted arrow) and the step bearings are displayed relative to the wind. The individual step bearings relative to wind direction for each step are represented by dots surrounding the circle. Overall, the orientation of Euclidian movement was influenced by the wind direction. Although movement relative to the wind was variable, a unimodal direction of movement upwind was observed when all monarchs were compared (A; Rayleigh test of uniformity: test statistic = 0.2316, $P = 0.0023$; Watson-Williams test for homogeneity of means: flight upwind = 0° , mean of movement = 5.47° , $F = 0.30965$, $df1 = 1$, 224, $P = 0.5784$). Additionally, monarchs that took large steps displayed a directional pattern of movement upwind (B; Rayleigh test of uniformity: test statistic = 0.442, $P = 0$; Watson-Williams test for homogeneity of means: flight upwind = 0° , mean of movement = -4.01° , $F = 0.2276$, $df1 = 1$, 144, $P = 0.634$).

To determine if geographic characteristics influenced the direction of movement, the orientation of Euclidian movement was analyzed by release location (S5) rather than the release habitat. Movement of monarchs at five of the release locations in the mosaic site and at the two roadside release locations displayed no directional pattern (Rayleigh test of uniformity: 0.2276 $>$ test statistic < 0.4838 , $P > 0.1209$). Monarchs released in MHD south of ZD (S5, location 6) had a directional pattern north-north-east toward HD (Rayleigh test of uniformity: test statistic = 0.4699, $P = 0.0537$; mean direction of movement = 7.4°). Monarchs released on the MHE between the east side of ZD and the west side of HD (S5, location 8) had a directional pattern southeast toward HD (Rayleigh test of uniformity: test statistic = 0.5512, $P = 0.0031$; mean direction of movement = 137.0°).

S23. Histograms of estimated female monarch perceptual distance to milkweed and/or blooming plants. Estimates of perceptual distance due to presumed visual or olfactory detection were made by summarizing step lengths associated with flight steps terminating on milkweed (A) or a nectar resource (B), independent of wind direction or step length. Estimates of perceptual distance due to presumed olfactory detection were estimated from steps > 30 m, oriented upwind, that terminated on a milkweed species (C) or a nectar resource (D). Bin widths in all histograms are 1 m. Note differences in y-axis scales.

Female Monarch Butterfly Movement and Habitat Utilization Patterns

S24. Histograms of turn angles (bins = 10°) created from three sequential georeferenced locations for female monarchs within each habitat class (rows) and either the mosaic site or the roadside sites (columns). Across all habitat classes, turn angles followed a normal distribution with narrow turn angles most common, which suggests highly directional movement. Within each habitat configuration, there was no difference in the distribution of turn angles in each habitat type (mosaic: $W = 8.6029$; $df = 6$; $P = 0.1972$; roadside: $W = 10.757$; $df = 6$; $P = 0.0962$). Likewise, there was no difference in the distributions of turn angles within HD (A and B; $W = 1.0684$, $df = 2$, $P = 0.5861$) or ZD (C and D; $W = 4.2617$, $df = 2$, $P = 0.1187$) when comparing the mosaic site to the roadside sites; however, the distributions of turn angles within LD (E and F; $W = 35.581$, $df = 2$, $P = 1.878e-08$) and HE (G and H) were wider in the mosaic site (E and G) than in roadside corridors (F and H; $W = 8.7208$, $df = 2$; $P = 0.01277$), likely because these habitats were linear at the roadside sites in comparison to the mosaic site.

S25. The numbers of sequential georeferenced locations, steps, and duration within each habitat class were analyzed with generalized linear models, which indicates monarchs were more active in areas with resources.

Measurement	Comparison	F ratio	Z ratio	df	P
Sequential	ZD x LD x HD x HE	5.995		3, 263	0.0004
Georeferenced	ZD x HE		1.253	1, 121	0.5933
Locations	ZD x LD		-1.096	1, 118	0.6918
	ZD x HD		-2.264	1, 110	0.1066
	HE x LD		-2.759	1, 153	0.0296
	HE x HD		-4.072	1, 145	0.0003
	LD x HD		-1.38	1, 142	0.5122
Sequential	ZD x LD x HD x HE	5.995		3, 263	0.0004
Steps	ZD x HE		1.253	1, 121	0.5933
	ZD x LD		-1.096	1, 118	0.6918
	ZD x HD		-2.264	1, 110	0.1066
	HE x LD		-2.759	1, 153	0.0296
	HE x HD		-4.072	1, 145	0.0003
	LD x HD		-1.38	1, 142	0.5122
Sequential	ZD x LD x HD x HE	5.995		3, 263	0.0004
Duration	ZD x HE		1.253	1, 121	0.5933
	ZD x LD		-1.096	1, 118	0.6918
	ZD x HD		-2.264	1, 110	0.1066
	HE x LD		-2.759	1, 153	0.0296
	HE x HD		-4.072	1, 145	0.0003
	LD x HD		-1.38	1, 142	0.5122

S26. Frequency of movements within, exiting, and entering each habitat class (colored bars; see Table 1 for abbreviations) across all spatial configurations. Significance at the 0.007 threshold to account for multiple comparisons is indicated within each movement category by different letters above the bars with the same color (values in S27).

S27. Percent of steps within and cross habitat boundaries were calculated and analyzed with multiple chi-square tests. Step lengths were analyzed by step category with glm.

Step Category	Comparison	% of Steps			Step length			
		χ^2	df	P	F ratio	Z ratio	df	P
Within	ZD x LD x HD x HE	151.75	3	< 2.2e-16	2.208		3, 583	0.0850
	ZD x HE	1.9931	1	0.158		1.351	1, 143	0.5303
	ZD x LD	60.662	1	6.776e-15		2.424	1, 294	0.0725
	ZD x HD	69.208	1	< 2.2e16		1.143	1, 306	0.6628
	HE x LD	81.724	1	< 2.2e16		0.599	1, 219	0.9323
	HE x HD	91.302	1	< 2.2e16		-0.488	1, 289	0.9618
	LD x HD	0.32579	1	0.5681		-1.560	1, 440	0.4017
Cross	ZD x LD x HD x HE	16.764	3	0.0007904	3.095		3, 199	0.0257
Boundary	ZD x HE	14.087	1	0.0001746		0.306	1, 90	0.9900
Exit	ZD x LD	13.462	1	0.0002435		0.710	1, 89	0.8932
	ZD x HD	5.2632	1	0.02178		-1.768	1, 74	0.2888
	HE x LD	0.007874	1	0.9293		0.542	1, 125	0.9488
	HE x HD	2.2857	1	0.1306		-2.517	1, 110	0.0574
Cross	LD x HD	2.027	1	0.1545		-2.869	1, 109	0.0214
	ZD x LD x HD x HE	21.308	3	9.083e-05	2.743		3, 197	0.0415
Boundary	ZD x HE	11.115	1	0.0008561		0.266	1, 102	0.9934
Enter	ZD x LD	0.58824	1	0.8084		-2.103	1, 66	0.1521
	ZD x HD	8.4949	1	0.003561		-0.437	1, 97	0.9721
	HE x LD	12.706	1	0.0003645		-2.808	1, 100	0.0256
	HE x HD	0.18797	1	0.6646		-0.891	1, 131	0.8096
	LD x HD	9.9072	1	0.001646		2.014	1, 95	0.1826

S28. Summary of interactions between monarchs and forage plants

Plant Species	Plant Common Name	Count	Duration (sec)		
			Min	Median	Max
<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i>	Black Eyed Susan	12	2	28	300
<i>Cirsium vulgare</i>	Bull Thistle	2	7	9.5	12
<i>Asclepias tuberosa</i>	Butterfly Milkweed	12	24	230	1500
<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	Common Milkweed	59	5	22	1740
<i>Taraxacum sp.</i>	Dandelion	17	4	57	190
<i>Ratibida pinnata</i>	Greyheaded Coneflower	3	42	117	1122
<i>Heliopsis helianthoides</i>	Oxeye Sunflower	11	13	31	275
<i>Echinacea pallida</i>	Pale Purple Coneflower	1	20	20	20
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	25	8	98	1377
<i>Asclepias incarnata</i>	Swamp Milkweed	2	33	57.5	82
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	15	1	75	274
<i>Melilotus albus</i>	White Sweet Clover	3	32	141	220
<i>Asclepias verticillata</i>	Whorled Milkweed	1	32	32	32
<i>Monarda fistulosa</i>	Wild Bergamot	88	2	39	1800
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	Yarrow	1	5	5	5
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	Chicory	1	180	180	180
<i>Verbena stricta</i>	Hoary Vervain	1	1161	1161	1161

S29. Summaries of step lengths performed by breeding-season female monarchs. Step lengths (\pm SD) were significantly larger when monarchs crossed a habitat boundary than when they moved within a habitat class (see Table 1 for abbreviations), as indicated by different letters above the bars (A). Step lengths based on movement within and across habitat boundaries by habitat class are displayed in B; colored bars represent habitat classes. Different letters above the bars in the same color represent significant differences at the $P = 0.05$ threshold (values in S27).

S30. Two-dimensional ordination of the first two principle components (PCs) from a principle components analysis of temperature, wind speed, and days captive for female monarchs that took at least one step > 50 m (blue) and those that did not (red). PC1 was negatively correlated with temperature (-0.918) and accounted for 49.36% of the total variation, PC2 was negatively correlated with wind speed (-0.914) and accounted for 47.95% of the variation, and PC3 was negatively correlated with days captive (-0.999) and accounted for 2.687% of the variation. Only variables with a correlation greater than ± 0.914 are included in the interpretation of the axes.

S31. References in Supporting Information

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